

DEVELOPMENT AND APPLICATION OF MODIFIED LYE FOR TREATING HYDROGEN SULPHIDE IN COAL MINE

Asadjon Kambarov

Teacher

Sabinabonu Ruziyeva

Sevinch Darkhanova

Zilola Pattayeva

Djonibek Egamberdiyev

Student

Almalyk branch of Tashkent State Technical University named after

I.A.Karimov info@tdtu.uz.

Abstract. To improve the absorption efficiency of alkaline liquor treated with hydrogen sulphide in coal mines, a single sodium carbonate lye was taken as the basic raw material to modify the absorption of lye by adding the surfactant sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate (SDBS) and the oxidant hydrogen peroxide. Respectively, the effects of different concentrations of surfactants and oxidants in sodium carbonate solution on the removal of hydrogen sulphide gas were investigated. The results show that the concentration of sodium carbonate solution is positively correlated with the removal rate of hydrogen sulphide. When the concentration of sodium carbonate solution increases to 2%, the initial removal rate of hydrogen sulphide is close to 100%, however, the problem of secondary dissipation of hydrogen sulphide is more significant after vibration. With the increase of SDBS and hydrogen peroxide concentration, the removal rate of hydrogen sulphide from sodium carbonate solution respectively increases to 93.1% and 86.2%. Finally, through experimental analysis and in situ measurements, the optimal ratio of the modified lye in the hydrogen

sulphide treatment of this experiment is as follows: the concentration of sodium carbonate solution is shown to be 2%, the concentration of surfactant is 0.4%, and the concentration of oxidant is 0.6%. On this basis, by comparing the 40,201 working face of Xiaozhuang Coal Mine with the 40,202 working face, it is concluded that the average removal rate of the modified lye is 93.5%, and the treatment effect of removing hydrogen sulphide is significant.

Keywords: Coal mines Hydrogen sulphide Response surface Alkaline liquor

Introduction. Hydrogen sulphide is a colourless, flammable gas with the characteristic foul odour of rotten eggs; It is one of several toxic and harmful gases in coal mines [1,2]. In recent years, with the continuous increase of mining depth, high concentrations of H₂S (relative to the safe concentration of 6.6 ppm) have emerged both at home and abroad. High concentrations of H₂S will not only corrode underground equipment, but also damage the health of underground workers, posing a severe threat to safe production [3-5]. High-sulphur coal is widely distributed in China. With the improvement of mining technology and the increase of mining depths, the possibility of an H₂S disaster is bound to increase, therefore it is necessary to discuss the prevention and control technology of coal mine H₂S.

Many scholars have explored the formation mechanism of hydrogen sulphide in coal mines. Simonton & King [6] have studied the pollution risk of hydrogen sulphide to groundwater and the potential public health hazards caused by hydrogen sulphide in the process of coal mining. Liu [7] et al. propose three modes of formation of hydrogen sulphide: bacterial sulphate reduction (BSR), thermochemical sulphate reduction (TSR), and igneous activity, and analysed and classified some modes of formation of hydrogen sulphide in a coal seam. Zhu [8] et al. explored the formation mechanism of hydrogen sulphide and found that hydrogen sulphide was generated under the action of BSR or TSR given sufficient organic matter and a reducing environment.

Previous research into the formation and occurrence conditions of hydrogen sulphide has provided theoretical bases for the treatment of hydrogen sulphide in coal mines. At present, catalytic desulfurisation technology is mainly used in the treatment of hydrogen sulphide in coal, particularly in the United States, Australia, and other countries [9,10]. The main measures used to remove hydrogen sulphide in Chinese coal mines are to regulate air volume and spray alkali liquor. Based on the characteristics of different adsorbents, Lin [11] et al. showed that adding surfactant in the form of sodium carbonate solution can improve the adsorption of hydrogen sulphide in coal. Lin [12] used a Fenton reagent to treat H₂S in mine water, studying the effects of H₂O₂ dosage, FeSO₄·7H₂O dosage, and pH value on the treatment effect of hydrogen sulphide, and the kinetics of hydrogen sulphide removal by Fenton reagent. Liang [13,14] employed the COMSOL multi-physics chemical reaction module to simulate the process of alkali injection into a coal seam, studying the reaction of sodium carbonate solution with hydrogen sulphide in the coal seam, and guided the alkali injection of the coal seam with reference to the simulation results. Mi [15] et al. explored the effect of CE doping on the adsorption of oxygen on the adsorbent surface and found that CE ion can be used as the carrier in an oxidation–reduction reaction, which can accelerate the oxygen transfer in the desulfurisation of coal. Wu [16,17] et al. studied the effect of microwave on the structure of CeO₂ doped ZnO adsorbent to remove H₂S.

Results and discussion. Effect of sodium carbonate concentration on H₂S removal efficiency Fig. 2 shows the effects of Na₂CO₃ concentration on H₂S removal efficiency. The results indicate that with the increase from 0% to 2% of Na₂CO₃ concentration, H₂S removal efficiency increases from 15.6% to 85.7%. Related results indicate that hydrogen sulphide is an acid gas [18], the dissociation process in water is divided into two steps. As shown in Eqns (2)–(4). Each time an equal amount of protons

is released, the generated protons were removed by increasing the concentration of the lye, causing Eq. (5) to move to the right, increasing the H₂S absorption rate [19].

However, when the sodium carbonate concentration exceeds 2%, the H₂S removal rate after vibrating gradually becomes stable. Related results indicate that CO₂ in the coal seam undergoes adsorption, hydrolysis and dissociation in water (Eqs. (6)–(9)) [20]. Meanwhile, the pKa value in Eq. (8) (the first dissociation step of H₂CO₃) and Eq. (9) (the first dissociation step of H₂S) are similar, therefore H₂S and CO₂ can be absorbed in similar pH solutions [21,22], CO₂ reacts with sodium carbonate solution through Eq. (10), and the consumption of sodium carbonate leads to the reverse reaction of Eq. (5), which is not conducive to the absorption of hydrogen sulphide.

In addition, the initial removal rate gradually approached 100%. By comparison, it is found that the removal efficiency curve after vibration is always lower than the initial removal efficiency curve, indicating that the sodium carbonate solution did not

completely absorb the hydrogen sulphide, and the hydrogen sulphide, after vibration, escapes from the absorption tail liquid. The study found that even if the sodium carbonate concentration is 3%, the H₂S gas is released after the absorption tail liquid is vibrated. This is because HS⁻ generated according to Eq. (5) is a chemically unstable ion, and HS⁻ is easily re-released into the air by H⁺ in the absorption solution of Eq. (11) [23,24]. Therefore, the single use of sodium carbonate as an absorption solution, cannot completely remove hydrogen sulphide gas. In the mine environment, the absorption liquid is diluted by the mine water and the water flow interferes

therewith, and the secondary release of H₂S will become greater.

The experimental data were further analysed using the Design-Expert software. Five experimental designs were generated and verified. As is shown by the data in Table 7, using the ratio from the Design-Expert software, the maximum absolute error between the predicted and the actual point is 0.69%. This proves the reliability of this method. Considering that excessive alkalinity of the solution will cause harm to equipment and personnel, and when the concentration of sodium carbonate solution is more than 2%, the absorption efficiency gradually tends to be flat, combining with the common disasters of hydrogen sulphide in coal mines, the effect can be achieved by using a smaller concentration of reagents in a certain range. Therefore, the optimum proportion of modified alkali liquor developed in this experiment is as follows: sodium carbonate solution concentration 2%, surfactant concentration 0.4%, and oxidant concentration 0.6%.

The field experiment was carried out in Xiaozhuang Coal Mine, Binxian County, Xianyang City, Shaanxi Province, China. The sulphur content and geological conditions of the 40,201 working face in Xiaozhuang Coal Mine were similar to those of the 40,202 working face. At present, the excessive concentration of hydrogen sulphide in these two working faces is mainly found during mining, as is the abnormal enrichment of hydrogen sulphide in the coal body. The destruction of the coal body results in the reduction of internal pressure of hydrogen sulphide and the emission of hydrogen sulphide gas from the coal seam, which causes the problem of short-term exceedance of safe limits thereon, imposing severe risks to safe production. To compare the effect of modified lye and common lye on the treatment of hydrogen sulphide in the working surface, the 1300-m mining distance of 40,201 working face and 40,202 working face was selected for field test. The change of hydrogen sulphide concentration in the return airway, the upper corner and the lower corner of the working face at different positions from the working face was measured separately. From Fig. 8, when ordinary lye is sprayed onto the 40,201 working surface, there will be a secondary over-limit situation. Before the ordinary lye is sprayed, within 700 m from the working surface of 40201, the situation of hydrogen sulphide overrun often occurs. The average concentration of hydrogen sulphide on the working surface is 4.01 ppm. This is because the coal seam is in a low-sulphur area at the initial stage of mining. The sulphur content, the formation and occurrence of hydrogen sulphide are low, the concentration of hydrogen sulphide enriched in this section is low, the hydrogen sulphide concentration after treatment is reduced to about 1.43 ppm on average, and the removal rate of hydrogen sulphide is 59.5%. The lye can reduce the hydrogen sulphide concentration to below the national safe limit (6.6 ppm). When the mining distance is between 700 and 990 m, the concentration of hydrogen sulphide at the upper angle of the 40,201 working surface reaches 45 ppm, and the average concentration of hydrogen sulphide is 16.74 ppm, which is 76% higher than the average concentration

in the initial stage of mining. This is due to the region being in the core area of the passive diffusion stage, where the wind continuously carries hydrogen sulphide and diffuses it upwards, and the high sulphur content in the region leads to the accumulation of hydrogen sulphide. The average concentration of hydrogen sulphide after treatment is reduced to 6.97 ppm, but this remained above the codified national safe value (6.6 ppm). The removal rate of hydrogen sulphide is only 57.7%. Ordinary lye could not meet practical project requirements in the treatment of high concentration hydrogen sulphide. The average concentration of hydrogen sulphide between 990 and 1300 m is 4.53 ppm, and the over-limit condition is less in this range. The average concentration after treatment is 1.96 ppm, and the removal rate is 59.4%. Combining the data of Figs. 1–3, it can be seen that the actual removal rate of the common lye is 59% on average. Compared with Figs. 8 and 9, the hydrogen sulphide over-limit situation in 40,202 working face is more serious than that in 40201 working face. The modified lye developed in this experiment was used to treat the hydrogen sulphide emitted from the 40,202 working face: therein, the hydrogen sulphide exceeds the limit within a 700 m mining distance. The average concentration of hydrogen sulphide emitted is 4.8 ppm, the average concentration after treatment is 1.14 ppm, and the removal rate is 86.3%. The hydrogen sulphide rushing out in the range of 700–990 m reached an average concentration of 17.06 ppm, and the concentration of hydrogen sulphide in the upper corner reached 50 ppm. After treatment, the concentration of hydrogen sulphide drops to 2.21 ppm on average, and the removal rate is 85.7%. Compared with Figs. 8 and 9, we can see that there is no secondary over-limit in the process of treatment using modified lye.

(a) The response surface of A and C

(b) The response surface of A and B

(c) The response surface of B and C

Conclusion.

(1) It was found, by the single elemental analysis, that when the concentration of SDBS was 0.7%, the initial removal rate was 98%, and the removal rate after vibration was 93.1%; when the concentration of hydrogen peroxide was greater than 0.4%, the removal rate after vibration was greater than the initial removal rate, the removal rate gradually stabilised after 0.6%.

(2) By combining the RSM model with the results of the single factor experiments, it is proposed that the optimal ratio of modified lye developed in this experiment was a 2% concentration of sodium carbonate solution, 0.4% concentration of surfactant, and 0.6% concentration of oxidant.

(3) Taking the 40,201 working face and 40,202 working face of Xiaozhuang Mine as the research object, tests were conducted by spraying ordinary lye and modified lye to treat hydrogen sulphide. The results show that the average removal rate of modified lye was 93.5%, using the modified lye to control the concentration of hydrogen sulphide in the working surface can reduce the concentration of hydrogen sulphide to a safe value (6.6 ppm), and the

References:

[1] Jin SQ, Ding YM, Yan AH, Zhang QQ, Li Q, Zhao F. H₂S management in 15# coal seam of fenghuangshan coal mines. *Procedia Eng* 2011;26:1490–4.

- [2] Bashipour FU, Khorasani SN, Rahimi A. H₂S reactive absorption from off-gas in a spray column: insights from experimental and modeling. *Chem Eng Technol* 2016;38(12):2137–45.
- [3] Tang L, Wang S, Zhu X, Zhu X, Guan Y, Chen S, et al. Feasibility study of reduction removal of thiophene sulfur in coal. *Fuel* 2018;234:1367–72.
- [4] Hai L, Wei W, Wang YN, Yu YJ. Study on the rapid removal of H₂S in underground coal mines. *J China Coal Soc* 2012;37(12):2065–9.
- [5] Xue HF, Wen FW, Jian HY, Feng W, Zhong JC. Genesis analyses of H₂S gas abnormality in gas of Bayi coal mine in Zaozhuang. *J. China Coal Soc* 2006;31(2):206–10.
- [6] Simonton DS, King S. Hydrogen sulfide formation and potential health consequences in coal mining regions. *Water Qual EXposure Health* 2013;5(2):85–92.
- [7] Liu M, Deng Q, Zhao F, Liu Y. Origin of hydrogen sulfide in coal seams in China. *Saf Sci* 2012;50(4):668–73.
- [8] Zhu G., Shui CZ., & Ying BL. Origin and Distribution of Hydrogen Sulfide in Oil-Bearing Basins, China[J]. *Acta Geologica Sinica*,83(6):1188-1201.
- [9] Xue-Hai FU, Wang WF, Yue JH, Wang F. Genesis analyses of H₂S gas abnormality in gas of Bayi coal mine in Zaozhuang. *J China Coal Soc* 2006;31(2):206–10.
- [10] Sikarwar, P., Kumar, U. K. A., Gosu, V., & Subbaramaiah V. Catalytic OXidative Desulfurization of DBT Using Green Catalyst (Mo/MCM-41) Derived from Coal Fly Ash[J]. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, 2018,6(2): S1041784075.
- [11] Liu K., Hao X. Advances in Intensive Geological Evaluation Methods of the Mature EXploration Areas[J]. *Journal of Southwest Petroleum University*, 2015.

[12] Lin H, Wang YN, Wei- WEI, Yu-Jiang YU. Treatment of H₂S in mine water using Fenton reagent. *J China Coal Society* 2012;37(10):1760–4.

[13] Bing L, Xin PY, Wei JS, Xiu PZ. Numerical simulation of lye injection into coal seams for governance of H₂S and its field applications. *J China Univ Min Technol* 2017;46(2):244–9.

[14] L. Wang H. Yin X. Yang Analysis for pressure transient of coalbed methane reservoir based on Laplace transform finite difference method[J] *Petroleum* 1 3 2015 S1982837889.

[15] Mi J, Feng G, Han L, Guo T, Zhu Y, Wang J. Modified semi-coke-supported cerium oxide-doped zinc ferrites for the removal of H₂S from coal gas. *Chem Eng Technol* 2012;35(9):1626–31.

[16] Wu M, Hu C, Feng Y, Fan H, Mi J. Microwave effects on the structure of CeO₂-doped zinc oxide sorbents for H₂S removal. *Fuel* 2015;146:56–9.

[17] Liu DJ, Zhou WG, Wu J. CeO₂-MnO_x/ZSM-5 sorbents for H₂S removal at high temperature. *Chem Eng J* 2016;284:862–71.

[18] Sun B, Sheng M, Gao W, Zhang LL, Chen JF. Absorption of nitrogen oxides into sodium hydroxide solution in a rotating packed bed with preoxidation by ozone. *Energy Fuels* 2017;31(10).

[19] Startsev AN. Hydrogen sulfide as a source of hydrogen production. *Russ Chem Bull* 2017;66(8):1378–97.

- [20] Kreulen H, Versteeg GF, Smolders CA. Selective removal of H₂S from sour gas with microporous membranes. Part I. Application in a gas-liquid system. *J Membr Sci* 2017;73(2–3):293–304.
- [21] Pokorna D, Carceller JM, Paclik L, Zabranska J. Biogas cleaning by hydrogen sulfide scrubbing and bio-oxidation of captured sulfides. *Energy Fuels* 2015;29(7):337842083.
- [22] Tilahun E, Sahinkaya E, Çalli B. A hybrid membrane gas absorption and bio-oxidation process for the removal of hydrogen sulfide from biogas. *Int Biodeterior Biodegrad* 2018;127:69–76.
- [23] Shen F, Liu J, Zhang Z, Dong Y, Gu C. Density functional study of hydrogen sulfide adsorption mechanism on activated carbon. *Fuel Process Technol* 2018;171:258–64.
- [24] Zhang JP, Sun Y, Wai M, Zhang L, Xu K. Preparation of steam activated carbon from black liquor by flue gas precipitation and its performance in hydrogen sulfide removal: Experimental and simulation works. *J Taiwan Inst Chem Eng* 2016;59:395–404.